

THE CODES USED BY A NON-NATIVE ENGLISH SPEAKER (FRENCH SPEAKER) IN ENGLISH CONVERSATION

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Abstract

It can be considered as a sociolinguistic phenomenon that always appear in every activity during speak or make a conversation. Two terms commonly heard today in language educators' public and professional lives are globalization and the social turn. One of the objectives of English conversation is an account of the unique features of English that they have found in the speech the produce that related with the choice of the vocabulary, the tones, diction, how to arrange a good statement in sentences and many more. For the non-native English as the European users of English it seems very difficult because the ornament and the feature of its language nature are totally delivered in a huge different scheme. This is what the research arranged and finds generally in English conversation by non-native English especially the French speaker when they speak in English in a conversation during a communication in daily scenes of discourses situational. The design of method used in this research is qualitative research methods. And from this research suggests researchers to understand the meaning remains the first language even want to do code-switching and this is expected to further research may be able to reference material and examine the transfer of language that does not comply with the rules of the language such as its structure but often times done in the community.

Keywords: Codes, Non-native English speaker, English Conversation

1. INTRODUCTION

Talk about English especially in conversation through non-native English we cannot separated with the aspect that call sociolinguistic. It can be considered as a sociolinguistic phenomenon that always appear in every activity during speak or make a conversation. Two terms commonly heard today in language educators' public and professional lives are *globalization* and *the social turn*. Both of these phenomena have had a significant impact on the field of sociolinguistic (Hornberger and McKay, 2010). It clearly described that sociolinguistic are very demanding aspect in the globalization era like now a day. From the development of the various culture and its implementation with the social aspect during urban or newest mode around the world.

More over a linguistic product of language contact, determined in various ways by the social circumstances in which it occurs. One of the principal challenges is various codes in application in making a conversation. The codes are to determine to what extent the social circumstances affect the form which the other codes take in any given case. As we will see in every situational aspect occurs in everyday activity during conversation using English for non-native English it will clearly appear. There is also a great deal of the social aspect and culture in sociolinguistic which emphasizes the linguistic and typological factors which shape with the codes in English. A code is often considered that the codes patterns found in any given context appear in conversation aspect with several things determined. Thus, it represented a choice among grammatical options, the vocabulary, the word the, diction etc, which are themselves defined by the contributing with a native language come from. Everyone can modify the way they speak depending on who they are with or what the situation is. When they do this, they are drawing on their sociolinguistic knowledge. And every time they change the way they speak, depending on their interlocutor or situation, they provide more sociolinguistic information that builds up the sociolinguistic knowledge in the community (Meyerhoff, 2006)

One of the objectives of English conversation is an account of the unique features of English that they have found in the speech the produce that related with the choice of the vocabulary, the tones, diction, how to arrange a good statement in sentences and many more. For the non-native English as the European users of English it seems very difficult because the ornament and the feature of its language nature are totally delivered in a huge different scheme. These features it is argued, describe a variety of English which they label with a norm that called a code. A code itself has several features as code mixing and code switching. The choice of this particular term is problematic because, as a construct, of the codes uses and generally refers to an overarching function of language, not to any specific set of features meaning forms themselves. However, non-native English do not make this distinction. This has resulted in considerable attention being given to a confusing use of linguistic terminology and

to the assumptions and theoretical for make a conversation using English. Language differences also play a role, when translation is required in later phases. This is the case in most studies with participants and main researcher having the same non-English native language (Van Nes, 2010).

This is what the research arranged and finds generally in English conversation by non-native English especially the French speaker when they speak in English in a conversation during a communication in daily scenes of discourses situational. This is the widespread phenomenon the writer would like to look into. This phenomenon will certainly block fluency progress, i.e. a condition when a native understands you and you understand him or her. This means to be fluent we have to be like the native and to be like them we have to communicate in a natural way.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Codes in English

The codes in English are the aspect that cannot separated when we want to produce a sentence. It is possible to refer to a language or a variety of a language as a *code*. The term is useful because it is neutral. Terms like *dialect*, *language*, *style*, *standard language*, *pidgin*, and *creole* are inclined to arouse emotions. In contrast, the ‘neutral’ term *code*, taken from information theory, can be used to refer to any kind of system that two or more people employ for communication (. (It can actually be used for a system used by a single person, as when someone devises a private code to protect certain secrets.) All of the above, then, are codes by this, admittedly loose, definition. What is interesting is the factors that govern the choice of a particular code on a particular occasion. Why do people choose to use one code rather than another, what brings about shifts from one code to another, and why do they occasionally prefer to use a code formed from two other codes by switching back and forth between the two or even mixing them?

Such questions as these assume that there are indeed few single-code speakers; people are nearly always faced with choosing an appropriate code when they speak. Very young children may be exceptions, as may learners of a new language (for a while at least) and the victims of certain pathological conditions. In general, however, when you open your mouth, you must choose a particular language, dialect, style, register, or variety – that is, a particular code. You cannot avoid doing so. Moreover, you can and will shift, as the need arises, from one code to another. Within each code there will also be the possibility of choices not all of which will have the same import because some will be more marked than others, i.e., will be more significant. The various choices will have different social meanings. What are some of the factors that influence the choices you make?

We will look mainly at the phenomenon of *code-switching* in bilingual and multilingual situations. However, many of the issues that we will see there will also arise with those codes which can be called sub-varieties of a single language, e.g., dialects, styles, and registers.

2.2 Code Switching and Code Mixing

The particular dialect or language that a person chooses to use on any occasion is a code, a system used for communication between two or more parties. It also indicated that it is unusual for a speaker to have command of, or use, only one such code or system. Command of only a single variety of language, whether it be a dialect, style, or register, would appear to be an extremely rare phenomenon, one likely to occasion comment. Most speakers command several varieties of any language they speak, and bilingualism, even multilingualism, is the norm for many people throughout the world rather than unilingualism. People, then, are usually required to select a particular code whenever they choose to speak, and they may also decide to switch from one code to another or to mix codes even within sometimes very short utterances and thereby create a new code in a process known as *code-switching*. Code-switching (also called code-mixing) can occur in conversation between speakers’ turns or within a single speaker’s turn. In the latter case it can occur between sentences (intersententially) or within a single sentence (intrasententially). Code-switching can arise from individual choice or be used as a major identity marker for a group of speakers who must deal with more than one language in their common pursuits. As Gal (1988, p. 247) says, ‘codeswitching is a conversational strategy used to establish, cross or destroy group boundaries; to create, evoke or change interpersonal relations with their rights and obligations.’ We will now look more closely at this phenomenon.

We are therefore turning to the issue of what brings a speaker to choose variety X of a language A rather than variety Y, or even language A rather than language B. What might cause a speaker to switch from variety X to variety Y or from language A to language B? A number of answers have been suggested, including solidarity, accommodation to listeners, choice of topic, and perceived social and cultural distance. In other words, the motivation of the speaker is an important consideration in the choice. Moreover, such motivation need not be at all conscious, for apparently many speakers are not aware that they have used one particular variety of a language rather than another or sometimes even that they have switched languages either between or within utterances. Equating in this instance code with language, we can describe two kinds of code-switching: situational and metaphorical. *Situational code-switching* occurs when the languages used change according to the situations in which the conversants find themselves: they speak one language in one situation and another in a different one. No topic change is involved. When a change of topic requires a change in the language used we have *metaphorical code-switching*. The interesting point here is that some topics may be discussed in either code, but the choice of code adds a distinct flavor to what is said about the topic. The choice encodes certain social values. Linguists have

found it very difficult to explain precisely when, linguistically and socially, code-switching occurs, i.e., what all the constraints are. However, there is broad agreement about the general principles that are involved.

Instances of situational code-switching are usually fairly easy to classify for what they are. What we observe is that one variety is used in a certain set of situations and another in an entirely different set. However, the changeover from one to the other may be instantaneous. Sometimes the situations are so socially prescribed that they can even be taught, e.g., those associated with ceremonial or religious functions. Others may be more subtly determined but speakers readily observe the norms. This kind of code-switching differs from diglossia. In diglossic communities the situation also controls the choice of variety but the choice is much more rigidly defined by the particular activity that is involved and by the relationship between the participants. Diglossia reinforces differences, whereas code-switching tends to reduce them. In diglossia too people are quite aware that they have switched from H to L or L to H. Code-switching, on the other hand, is often quite subconscious: people may not be aware that they have switched or be able to report, following a conversation, which code they used for a particular topic.

As we have seen, your choice of code also reflects how you want to appear to others, i.e., how you want to express your identity and/or how you want others to view you. This is apparent from various *matched-guise* experiments that certain social psychologists have conducted. If person A is perfectly bilingual in languages X and Y, how is he or she judged as a person when speaking X? How do the same judges evaluate A when A is speaking language Y? In matched guise experiments the judges are unaware that they are judging A twice and that the only variable is that A is using language X on one occasion and language Y on the other, and using each for the same purpose. Their judgments, therefore, really reflect their feelings about speakers of X and Y, feelings about such matters as their competence, integrity, and attractiveness.

2.3 Code Switching and Code Mixing in Conversational/Pragmatic motivations

Myers-Scotton (1993a:49) drew a distinction between the “allocational” paradigm, in which social structure determines language behaviour, and the “interactional” one, in which individuals make “rational choices” to achieve their goals (p. 49). Milroy and Gordon (2003: Chapter 8) similarly contrast pragmatic uses of CS which exploit the symbolism or connotations of each of the codes, and those which purely exploit the contrast which the two varieties provide, regardless of their connotations. They emphasize the need to pay attention to both aspects in order to achieve a full understanding of CS.

Gumperz (1982) provided examples of both uses of CS. Using the distinction, between the we-code and the they-code, he described the conversational functions of CS with examples from Slovenian–German, Hindi–English and Spanish–English CS in the USA. He conceded that the range of interpretations that results is much greater than one would expect from describing the language usage in terms of the simple “we” and “they” dichotomy.

Goffmann’s concept of footing, developed with reference to monolingual speech, is highly relevant in CS: “A change in footing implies a change in the alignment we take up to ourselves and others present as expressed in the way we manage the production or reception of an utterance” (1979:5). Gumperz referred to CS as a “contextualization cue”, that is a “verbal or nonverbal cue that provides an interpretive framework for the referential content of a message” (1982:131). His list of conversational functions coinciding with switches also includes quotation, addressee specification, interjection, reiteration, message qualification and personalization v. objectification.

In Gardner-Chloros, Charles and Cheshire (2000), a direct comparison is made between the functions which CS has been shown to fulfil in bilingual conversations, and the equivalent expression of these functions in a monolingual context. Two assumptions were made. The first is that bilingual code-switchers and monolinguals accomplish basically the same conversational functions with the different means at their disposal. Bell writes, for example: “having two discrete languages available rather than a continuum of styles simply throws into sharper focus the factors which operate on monolingual style-shifting. The social processes are continuous across all kinds of language situations” (1984:176). The second assumption is that, except in the case of “unmarked” CS, it is more likely that switches are functional than non-functional. Whether such switches are an instance of “rational choices” in Myers-Scotton’s terms, or simply capitalize on contrasts within the conversation, we expected most genuine switches be motivated.

A different view on ascribing motivations to CS is provided by Stroud (1992; 1998). Stroud studied CS in a non-Western context, between Tok Pisin (one of the three national languages of PapuaNew Guinea) and Taiap, a language spoken in the village of Gapun by a mere eighty-nine people. He pointed out the inapplicability, in this context, of Gumperz’s “in-group/out-group” view of bilingualism, as he claims that no domain, speech genre or topic is conducted exclusively in one language. More fundamentally, he criticizes the whole notion of “intentionality”, which he claims is based on an inappropriate, Western view of “personhood”. Drawing on work by Duranti (1988), and Hill and Hill (1986), itself influenced by the Bakhtinian notion of “voices” (or points of view on the world), he claims that CS in Gapun should be seen as a series of rhetorical moves which highlight contrasts, and/or perceptual shifts providing different points of view on a situation. “The words of others carry with them their own expression, their own evaluative tone, which we assimilate, re-work and re-accentuate” (Bakhtin, 1986:89). There is little doubt that CS can provide different “voices” to the same speaker. This finding ties in with research on reported speech in monolingual contexts: Tannen (1989), for example, points out that most reported speech is “constructed dialogue”, i.e. has never in fact been spoken.

2.4 Code Switching and Code Mixing in Accommodation, attitudes and audience design

Compared with other areas, there is a relative lack of work on the social psychological aspects of CS, although the concepts used by social psychologists are extremely relevant to an understanding of it and such results which exist should be seen as complementary to research on other aspects (Sachdev and Bourhis, 2001).

CS is one of the possible ways of accommodating to the interlocutor's linguistic preferences. It can serve as a compromise between two varieties, where these carry different connotations or social meanings for speakers and interlocutors. It may also, of course, be the only possibility open to a speaker where there is a mismatch between their level of competence in the relevant languages and that of their interlocutor.

This compromise function – particularly where it allows the speaker to address an audience made up of people with disparate linguistic competences – is not limited to spontaneous speech. It is also exploited by politicians in their speeches and comedians in their jokes (Woolard, 1988). Generally, it is used in the media which are aimed at multilingual audiences for multiple functions.

Attitude studies of CS are still relatively few and far between, and most of our information on this is gleaned from a variety of studies where responses are elicited about attitudes along with other aspects. An early exception to this was Chana and Romaine (1984), who reported negative attitudes towards CS among Punjabi–English bilinguals in Birmingham, in spite of their almost exclusively using a CS mode. Bentahila (1983) carried out a matched guise experiment among 109 Arabic–French bilinguals in Morocco, and found a large majority expressing disapproval of the CS guise, with attitudes ranging from pity to disgust. Gibbons (1987) found similar reactions among Cantonese–English code-switching students in Hong Kong, although he also identified an element of covert prestige associated with it. Gumperz's subjects attributed CS to characteristics such as lack of education, bad manners or language inability (1991), and Zentella's to language deficiency, rather than language skill or discourse needs (1997).

2.5 Code Switching and Code Mixing in Gender

Gender is considered one of the most important sociolinguistic categories. Studies of the interaction of gender with linguistic performance have become increasingly subtle, avoiding the facile generalizations of the 1970s studies. Gender has assumed more prominence within the discipline rather than less, as the ways in which it is studied have become more diversified.

The long-established finding that women use more standard forms than men (Labov, 1972; Trudgill, 1972; Chambers, 2003) derives from monolingual settings. In its simplest form, it can usefully be tested in bilingual contexts. First, we need to know whether, in a given case, the choice of one or the other variety corresponds with a choice between the vernacular and the prestige code. In some cases, it is the CS mode itself, as we have seen, which carries the “ingroup” connotations and may be considered the “local” type of speech (Swigart, 1991).

3. METHOD

3.1 Design

The design of method used in this research is qualitative research methods. Kirk and Miller (1986, p. 9) defines that qualitative research is a particular tradition in social science that fundamentally depends on the observations in humans in its own region and in touch with these people in a language and in its idiom. The techniques that are used in qualitative research are interactive cover depth interviews (elite interviews), observation and non-interactive role includes questioners, archive (content analysis). This is according to Goetz and LeCompte in Sutopo (2006, p. 66) argued that the data collection strategies in qualitative research in general could be divided into two kinds of ways, which is a technique of data that is interactive and non-interactive.

3.2 Subject

The subjects of this research are the French speaker tourists with the range of age between 23 to 50 years old. They come and visit Indonesia as a tourist. And then majority the French speaker tourist they only speak with their native language but not fluently speak in English.

4. FINDING

4.1 Expression of Code-Switching and Code-Mixing

From this study the data code-mixing and code-switching is obtained as follows:

All the conversation included Code-Switching and Code-Mixing Expression in English - French

Conversation 1	
X	good morning
Y	good morning
X	This is Rene
X	how are you?
Y	fine I'm Okay
X	where are you now can you explain Rene?
Y	On est a Probolinggo ou sorry we are in Probolinggo

X	what do you see here?
Y	il y a beaucoup a bateau de peche ohhh sorry the ship or sheep for looking a fish..for a fisherman..
X	Oo okay thank you
Y	Merci.
Conversation 2	
X	Please meet francis he is from belgique a tourist who speak French
X	How are you francis?
Y	Cava bien ohhh I'm okay
X	What your comment about Indonesia?
Y	C'est magnifique oohh sorry that is very beautiful ..awesome...
Y	By the way on est le troisieme place on the title in world cup this annee..
X	Congratulation I mean... Thank you...
Y	Thank you...
Conversation 3	
X	Vous vous s'appelle comment ou what your name?
Y1, Y2	I'm cindy, I'm Margo
X	Comment what your come from?
Y2	I'm habite a Paris
X	Ooo Paris good
X	How are you today?
Y1	I'm cava okay fine merci
X	Demain on va au volcan tomorrow we going to hike to the mountain
Y2	Wooo magnifique amazing
X	On se leve a 4 heure du matin at 4.00 o'clock at the morning
Y2	Sure?? Yeaahh sureee
X	Vous etes fatigue girls?
Y1	Oohhhh yess of course but cava cava bien
X	Oke thank you merci,,merci...
Conversation 4	
X	expliquer about the equipe de France?
Y	Ohhh that is good en ce moment
Y	Tous les footbaleurs play good and mieux en terrain
X	What is your favourite player?
Y	Tous les football player France are better today
Y	It's a composition mélange entre all the european and Afrique footballeur
X	How about Olivier Giroud?
Y	He is play good on terrain et il pratique a good football
X	But he never score a goal?
Y	Il garde or what it is mean he guard a ball in the middle
Y	He is awesome player
Y	We never have a footballeur like him
Y	Cest le meilleur footballeur in the middle terrain
X	Oke merci....thank you very much
Y	Oke thank you....
Conversation 5	
X	What your comment about the France national football?
Y	What??
X	Quelle e st votre commentaire about equipe de France?
Y	En English ou en France?
X	Okay you can explain en France?
Y	Okay....ennnn depuis que on a les deux etoiles on est le meilleur maintenant.
X	D'accord okay
Y	Bon non je ne connais pas plus sur le football , je connais aucun j'aime pas le football. Je reagarder mais je ne connais pas beaucoup.
X	You like tennis? Je connait sur a votre chaussures
Y	Oui Jaime bien tennis et je jouer tennis
Y	Mais en generale maintenant equipe de France cetait beacoup mieux
X	Okay thank you merci
Y	Thank you merci that is all...lol
X	Okay let's go..... ces't parti mon kiki

Y	Lol lol lol
Conversation 6	
X	On est a ijen maintenant (we are on the top of mount ijen now)
X	Cest Patrick il est Suisse (he is Patrick, he is come from swiss)
X	What your commentaire sur le football Suisse Patrick?
Y	C'est good now we have beaucoup football player from tout le monde now
X	Woooo that is good
X	What is your favorite football player?
Y	What ?
X	I mean quel est votre footbaleur prefere?
Y	Hmmm that is difficile to parle lol
X	How about Xhaka (name of the football player)?
Y	Il pas bien, il pas bien joue..
X	Ahhhh because maybe his tempered or the other?
Y	Ohhhh il toujuor pas bien ...il pas bien..hhhh
Y	Shaqiri est TOP..
X	Ahhhh Shaqiri I know...he is very famous here. On est connait bien en Indonesie
Y	C'est sure?
X	Yes oui...
X	Okay merci..salut..
Y	Salut...

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Observation

The results of observation from the study are to find code mixing and code switching used by French speaker tourist who speak English. It is considered suitable to the topic of natural conversation about light events during research conducted. Location of research subjects are: Probolinggo at Pasir Putih Beach, Ijen Mountain Banyuwangi and on the rice field during a trip to go to Ijen Mountain Banyuwangi

5.2 Interview

Interviews were conducted to 7 people (French speaker tourist that consisted from French, Belgium and Swiss) in each interview with a conversation model conducted to obtain in-depth data on the use of more than one language in the society. Data obtained from the interviews is detailed community data is the reason why they use more than one language in a conversation and the data contained in the data is the reason for using code-switching and code-mixing. Apart from that, the researchers also asked direct interviews phrase commonly spoken in everyday conversation in which the sentence contains more than one language and the data is contained in the data code-switching and code-mixing in the fit on the next discussion.

5.3 Archive

In the analysis of the documents, data was taken from a written speech and recorded audio visual of the French speaking tourist. Data obtained from the document is not so much because most of the written speech used in one language only. But its application in the delivery of the speaker is usually mixed with other languages according to the listener is in the chamber. For information on data obtained from analysis of these documents already contained in the existing data in the subsequent discussion.

5.4 Analysis of Level of Code-Switching and Code-Mixing

1) Code Switching and Code Mixing in Conversational/Pragmatic motivations.

For the classification of the Code Switching and Code Mixing in Conversational/Pragmatic motivations in a sentence as follows.

fine I'm Okay
On est a Probolinggo ou sorry we are in Probolinggo
il y a beaucuop a bateau de peche ohhh sorry the ship or sheep for looking a fish..for a fisherman..
Cava bien ohhh I'm okay
C'est magnifique oohh sorry that is very beautiful ..awesome...
By the way on est le troisieme place on the title in world cup this annee..
I'm habite a Paris
I'm cava okay fine merci
Wooo magnifique amazing
Oohhhh yess of course but cava cava bien
Ohhh that is good en ce moment
Tous les footbaleurs play good and mieux en terrain
Tous les football player France are better today

It's a composition mélange entre all the eupean and Afrique footballeur
He is play good on terrain et il pratique a good football
Il garde or what it is mean he guard a ball in the middle
C'est le meilleur footballeur in the middle terrain
Okay....ennnn depuis que on a les deux etoiles on est le meilleur maintenant.
Thank you merci that is all...lol
C'est good now we have beaucoup football player from tout le monde now
Hmmm that is difficile to parle lol
Shaqiri est TOP..
C'est sure?
Okay merci..salut..

2) Code Switching and Code Mixing in Accommodation, attitudes and audience design

For the classification of the Code Switching and Code Mixing in Accommodation, attitudes and audience design in a sentence as follows.

good morning
fine I'm Okay
Cava bien ohhh I'm okay
C'est magnifique oohh sorry that is very beautiful ..awesome...
By the way on est le troisieme place on the title in world cup this annee..
I'm cava okay fine merci
Wooo magnifique amazing
Sure?? Yeaahh sureee
Oohhhh yess of course but cava cava bien
We never have a footballeur like him
En English ou en France?
Thank you merci that is all...lol
Hmmm that is difficile to parle lol
Shaqiri est TOP..
C'est sure?
Okay merci..salut..

3) Code Switching and Code Mixing in Gender

For the classification of the Code Switching and Code Mixing in Gender in a sentence as follows.

il y a beaucuop a bateau de peche ohhh sorry the ship or sheep for looking a fish..for a fisherman..
By the way on est le troisieme place on the title in world cup this annee..
Tous les football player France are better today
It's a composition mélange entre all the european and Afrique footballeur
He is play good on terrain et il pratique a good football
Il garde or what it is mean he guard a ball in the middle
He is awesome player
We never have a footballeur like him
Cest le meilleur footballeur in the middle terrain
Oui Jaime bien tennis et je jouer tennis
Shaqiri est TOP..

6. CONCLUSION

From the results and discussion above, we can conclude that code-switching and code-mixing that produce by non-native English speaker especially the French speaking English are categories in 3 aspect found. And from this research suggests researchers to understand the meaning remains the first language even want to do code-switching and this is expected to further research may be able to reference material and examine the transfer of language that does not comply with the rules of the language such as its structure but often times done in the community.

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